

EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

UP TO
YOUTH

Erasmus+

Youth

EUROPEAN UNION

EU YOUTH DIALOGUE

EU YD11 Implementation Phase Report

Implemented under the Cypriot Presidency of the Council of the European Union

Based on the Reports of the EU Youth Dialogue National Working Groups

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Executive Summary

This is an implementation report of the 11th Cycle of the European Union Youth Dialogue (EUYD11) overseen jointly by the Trio Presidency of Poland, Denmark, and Cyprus. This implementation report is based on contributions from the EUYD National Working Groups (NWGs) from the EU Member States, National Youth Councils from the EU candidate countries, and international youth non-governmental organisations (IYNGOs).

What did the implementation phase of the EUYD11 focus on?

The EUYD11 implementation phase focused on European Youth Goal no.1 ("*Connecting EU with Youth*") and recommendations from the Lublin and Copenhagen EU Youth Conferences. This Youth Goal seeks to bridge the gap between the EU and young people to rebuild trust.

What implementation activities were reported?

In total, 205 implementation activities were reported, with 94% coming from the EU Member States. Most initiatives focused on:

- information campaigns (42%),
- activities by, for and with young people (38%), and
- policy development (31%).

What subgoals of the European Youth Goal no.1 were tackled?

All implementation activities covered European Youth Goal no.1, targeting mostly up to two subgoals to stay as focused as possible (over 60% of all activities). Almost 60% of these initiatives tackled meaningful youth involvement in EU decision-making and over 50% tackled equal access to quality, impartial, and youth-friendly information.

What recommendations from the EU Youth Conferences in Lublin and Copenhagen were tackled?

The EU Member States, the EU candidate countries, and the IYNGOs were also offered an opportunity to identify if and what recommendations created at the EU Youth Conferences in Lublin (Poland) and Copenhagen (Denmark) were covered by their implementation activities. Overall, coverage of these recommendations was limited. Only slightly over half of all implementation activities addressed any of the Lublin recommendations, focusing primarily on:

- strengthening youth engagement in decision-making (44%), and
- introducing mandatory civic education (20%).

Coverage of the Copenhagen recommendations was even lower, with nearly two-thirds of activities failing to address any of them. The implementation activities that tackled the Copenhagen recommendations mostly focused on:

- ensuring that the upcoming Erasmus+ programme addresses external challenges (21%), and
- supports youth volunteering and solidarity (19%).

How did the EU-level actors contribute?

Furthermore, this report also includes contributions from EU-level actors: Denmark and Poland (part of the Trio of the Presidency of the Council of the EU), the European Commission (DG EAC), and the European Youth Forum (YFJ).

The Danish and Polish Presidencies generally contributed to the EUYD11 implementation by hosting EU Youth Conferences in Copenhagen and Lublin, and by translating youth recommendations into policy documents such as Council Conclusions. They further strengthened youth voices by facilitating direct dialogue between youth and decision-makers, and by driving policy changes at the EU and national levels, such as Poland's introduction of compulsory civic education.

The European Commission (DG EAC) acted on the EUYD11 outcomes by assessing and disseminating recommendations, including references to the EUYD in key documents, such as the European Democracy Shield, or the Strategy for LGBTIQ Equality. Furthermore, DG EAC facilitated high-level policy exchanges and is strengthening voices of young people during the revision of the EU Youth Strategy. DG EAC also used recommendations from the EUYD11 to:

- support the revision of the EU Youth Dialogue governance, and
- set up a planned National Working Groups (NWG) meeting in May 2026.

The European Youth Forum (YFJ) advanced EUYD11 by disseminating EUYD11 outcomes and by conducting high-level advocacy meetings with representatives of the EU Member States, specifically tackling the upcoming Erasmus+ programme and emphasizing the Danish policy recommendations.

How can the implementation phase be further improved?

Twenty-three stakeholders highlighted several key areas for improving the EUYD implementation phase. To reduce uncertainty, they called for clearer definitions of the phase's objectives and more efficient practical management regarding funding and timelines. Many emphasized the need for capacity building, stronger international cooperation, and a more robust communication system designed to share the tangible impacts of the EUYD directly with young people.

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Introduction

This is an implementation report of the 11th Cycle of the European Union Youth Dialogue (EUYD11) overseen jointly by the Trio Presidency of Poland, Denmark, and Cyprus. This implementation report is based on contributions from the EUYD National Working Groups (NWGs) based in the EU Member States, from National Youth Councils of the EU candidate countries, and from international youth non-governmental organisations (IYNGOs). These contributions were guided by the “*EUYD11 Implementation Phase Reporting Instructions*” prepared and presented by the European researchers under the Danish Presidency of the Council of the European Union.

Furthermore, this report also includes contributions from the EU-level actors: two of the countries that are currently part of the Trio of the Presidency of the Council of the EU, namely Denmark and Poland; representatives of the European Commission, specifically the Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture (DG EAC); and the representatives of the European Youth Forum (YFJ).

Overall, the EUYD11 implementation phase focused on the European Youth Goal no.1 “*Connecting EU with Youth*”, as well as on recommendations created at the EU Youth Conferences in Lublin (Poland) and in Copenhagen (Denmark). The European Youth Goal no.1 aims to “*Foster the sense of youth belonging to the European project and build a bridge between the EU and young people to regain trust and increase participation*”, and the recommendations from both EU Youth Conferences are featured as annexes to this report.

All relevant stakeholders were asked what implementation activities were taking place or were planned to take place which were directly linked to any of the targets of the European Youth Goal no.1 “*Connecting EU with Youth*”. Optionally, the stakeholders were also invited to list any implementation activities directly related to the outcomes of the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland), the outcomes of the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark), or the outcomes of the consultation phase of the EUYD11. The “*EUYD11 Implementation Phase Reporting Instructions*” also provided the NWGs with a reporting template and a link to an online form through which the data were reported back to the EUYD Steering Group in February 2026.

All in all, 27 National Working Groups (NWGs) from 25 EU Member States submitted the implementation reporting data, namely:

- | | |
|---|--------------------|
| • Austria (AT) | • Greece (GR) |
| • Belgium - German-speaking Community (BE-DE) | • Hungary (HU) |
| • Belgium - French Community (BE-FR) | • Ireland (IE) |
| • Belgium - Flemish Community (BE-FL) | • Italy (IT) |
| • Bulgaria (BG) | • Latvia (LV) |
| • Cyprus (CY) | • Lithuania (LT) |
| • Czech Republic (CZ) | • Luxembourg (LU) |
| • Denmark (DK) | • Malta (MT) |
| • Estonia (EE) | • Netherlands (NL) |
| • Finland (FI) | • Poland (PL) |
| • France (FR) | • Portugal (PT) |
| • Germany (DE) | • Slovakia (SK) |
| | • Slovenia (SI) |
| | • Spain (ES) |
| | • Sweden (SE) |

Note: Country abbreviations are listed as they are used throughout this report to refer to the NWG origin.

Moreover, two international youth NGOs (IYNGOs) submitted their contributions as well as, namely:

- AEGEE-EUROPE, and
- Erasmus Student Network (ESN).

Finally, two EU candidate countries also contributed, namely Montenegro (ME) and Moldova (MD).

In total, 205 different implementation activities were reported by NWGs based in the EU Member States, NYCs of the EU candidate countries, and IYNGOs. The whole set of 205 activities is explored in the next chapter in some detail. Furthermore, separate analyses are presented for contributions from the EU Member States, from the EU candidate countries, and from the IYNGOs, in the following chapters as well.

An additional set of activities was reported by the EU-level stakeholders, namely by the European Commission, two of the Trio of countries holding the Presidency of the Council of the EU in 2025 and 2026 (Poland and Denmark), and the European Youth Forum (YFJ). This additional set of activities is also explored in a separate dedicated chapter.

This implementation report focuses on exploring what specific areas of the European Youth Goal no.1 were covered by the implementation activities, and by various stakeholders. All statistics are rounded to the nearest whole number.

1. What Implementation Activities Were Reported Overall?

Firstly, it is important to notice that **all of the EU Member States, EU candidate countries, and IYNGOs that submitted the reports contributed to the implementation phase of the EUYD11 rather evenly**. This can be seen in Figure 1, which shows that most of the countries and IYNGOs submitted similar shares of implementation activities. There are exceptions, such as Poland, Belgium (counted for the whole country) or Germany which submitted larger numbers of implementation activities, or Italy and Bulgaria which submitted fewer implementation activities, but in most cases, we see 2-5% of implementation activities per actor. This is a positive result, because it means that in most of these countries and IYNGOs, the EUYD11 was implemented through a similar number of implementation initiatives.

When exploring how various countries contributed to the implementation phase of the EUYD11, Figure 2 shows that **indeed among the countries the top three contributors to the implementation of the EUYD11 were Poland (10%), Belgium (9% as a combined result for all three communities), and Germany (7%)**, while the fewest numbers of contributions came from Italy (1%) and Bulgaria (1%), with other countries contributing rather evenly.

Overall, 94% of the implementation activities were reported by the EU Member States, 2% by EU candidate countries, and 3% by IYNGOs (see Figure 3).

The EU Member States, EU candidate countries, and IYNGOs were asked to indicate what type of implementation activities they submitted (see Figure 5 for a list and description of all activity types). They could indicate more than one type per implementation activity in order to allow them to describe even more complex cases. Figure 4 shows that **more than half of all submitted implementation activities were substantially focused**, and they could be described using 1 or 2 activity types. Moreover, about 90% of all submitted implementation activities were described using up to 4 activity types, suggesting some of the activities to be complex and multi-pronged ones.

Figure 6 further shows that the most common implementation activity reported by EU Member States, EU candidate countries, and IYNGOs, were general information raising campaigns focusing on the EU Youth Dialogue, and programmes and activities for young people. Each of these two types were represented by about 40% of all submitted implementation activities. Moreover, policy development and high-level dialogue as well as other dialogue activities between young people and policymakers represented about a third of all submitted implementation activities. This suggests that **most of the implementation activities focused on information campaigns, hands-on activities by, for and with young people, and policy-focused initiatives.**

Figure 1: Shares of Implementation Activities Reported by Different Actors.

Figure 3: Shares of Implementation Activities Reported by Different Types of Stakeholders.

Figure 4: Shares of Numbers of Activity Types per Implementation Activity.

Figure 5: Typology of Implementation Activities.

Type of Implementation Activity	
Policy development & high-level dialogue	Such as policy and strategy work towards the incorporation of the EUYD results into national policies or agendas, e.g.: dialogue with national stakeholders such as meeting with ministerial representatives, structured policy development process such as incorporation of the EUYD results into national strategies.
Other dialogue activities between young people and policymakers	Such as activities that enable general dialogue between decision makers and young people such as local youth conferences and consultation activities.
Capacity building of stakeholders	Such as training, support programmes and other activities to develop the competencies of stakeholders who work with young people.
Programmes and activities for young people	Such as activities with the main aim to educate, support, or in some way provide benefits to the young people taking part in the activity.
Information campaigns sharing results of the EU Youth Dialogue with young people	Closing the EU Youth Dialogue circle and informing young people about the results of the current cycle of the EUYD, or how the current EUYD results have been or will be implemented, applied, or otherwise utilised in the national, regional, or local context.
General information or awareness raising campaigns about the EU Youth Dialogue	Such as information campaigns to inform young people about the EU Youth Dialogue and opportunities to participate, either now or in the future.
General information or awareness raising campaigns about the European Youth Goal n.1 “Connecting EU with Youth”	Such as information campaigns relating to the EU values, or opportunities for young people across the EU.
Advocacy & campaigns	Such as lobbying activities by National Youth Councils.
Development of structures for youth participation	Such as creation or improvement of youth advisory groups.
Resource production	Such as the creation of guides and toolkits for youth workers.
Funding related initiatives	Such as the development of new funding schemes.

Figure 6: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity.

Figure 7: Shares of Numbers of European Youth Goal no.1 Subgoals Covered by Implementation Activities.

Figure 8: Shares of European Youth Goal no.1 Subgoals Covered by Implementation Activities.

Figure 9: Shares of Numbers of Recommendations from the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland) Covered by Implementation Activities.

Implementation activities were all connected to the European Youth Goal no.1 “*Connecting EU with Youth*”, and the stakeholders were asked to identify what subgoals specifically their activities covered. Figure 7 shows that **two thirds of all reported implementation activities were highly focused and covered no more than two subgoals**. Over 80% of all activities covered maximum of three subgoals, and over 90% covered a maximum of four subgoals. **This shows that while the efforts to cover more than one subgoal are obvious, the implementation activities were still designed to stay as focused as possible.**

Figure 8 shows what specific subgoals of the European Youth Goal no.1 were tackled. There are two domains which were covered by more than half of all implementation activities: meaningful youth involvement in EU decision-making; and equal access to quality, impartial, and youth-friendly information. Furthermore, there are another two domains which were tackled by over 40% of all implementation activities, namely: increase of education about Europe and the EU; and building young people’s trust in the EU. Surprisingly, given the focus of the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark), only 13% of all implementation activities tackled the subgoal focusing on improving the EU youth programmes.

The EU Member States, the EU candidate countries, and the IYNGOs were also offered an opportunity to identify if and what recommendations created at the EU Youth Conferences in Lublin (Poland) and Copenhagen (Denmark) were covered by their implementation activities.

Figure 9 shows that almost half of all implementation activities did not cover any recommendation created at the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland), and only 35% of all implementation activities covered one of these recommendations. **All in all, only slightly more than half of all implementation activities covered at least one of the recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland).**

The two most tackled recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland) were the ones focusing on strengthening of youth engagement in decision-making (44%) and on introducing civic education as a mandatory subject in formal education. Figure 10 also shows that all other recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland) were only tackled marginally through the EUYD11 implementation activities.

Figure 10: Shares of Recommendations from the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland) Covered by Implementation Activities.

Figure 11: Shares of Numbers of Recommendations from the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark) Covered by Implementation Activities.

Figure 12: Shares of Recommendations from the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark) Covered by Implementation Activities.

Recommendations from the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark) were covered even less in the EUYD11 implementation activities. Figure 11 shows that almost two thirds of implementation activities did not tackle any of the recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark), 16% tackled one of them, and only 22% tackled two or more. This may be connected to the fact that the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark) came rather late in the EUYD11 cycle, and therefore it might have been difficult to incorporate the recommendations into the workplans. Another reason for low coverage of these recommendations may also lie with their topical focus: Since they all addressed the design of the upcoming youth mobility programme, Erasmus+ 2028-2034, they are necessarily rather specific and focused on the EU level, and that may have posed yet another barrier to the various stakeholders designing implementation activities in EUYD11.

The recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark) that were tackled the most in the EUYD11 implementation activities were the ones on making sure that the upcoming Erasmus+ programme will address external challenges faced by young people (21%) and that the upcoming Erasmus+ programme will ensure a dedicated space for youth volunteering and solidarity (19%). Figure 12 also shows that even though the recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark) were not used extensively in the EUYD11 implementation phase, none of these recommendations was completely left out either.

2. What Activities Were Implemented in the EU Member States?

This section summarises only the implementation activities collected and submitted by the National Working Groups (NWGs) of the EU Member States, namely:

- | | |
|---|--------------------|
| • Austria (AT) | • Greece (GR) |
| • Belgium - German-speaking Community (BE-DE) | • Hungary (HU) |
| • Belgium - French Community (BE-FR) | • Ireland (IE) |
| • Belgium - Flemish Community (BE-FL) | • Italy (IT) |
| • Bulgaria (BG) | • Latvia (LV) |
| • Cyprus (CY) | • Lithuania (LT) |
| • Czech Republic (CZ) | • Luxembourg (LU) |
| • Denmark (DK) | • Malta (MT) |
| • Estonia (EE) | • Netherlands (NL) |
| • Finland (FI) | • Poland (PL) |
| • France (FR) | • Portugal (PT) |
| • Germany (DE) | • Slovakia (SK) |
| | • Slovenia (SI) |
| | • Spain (ES) |
| | • Sweden (SE) |

In total, the NWGs from the EU Member States submitted 195 implementation activities, and this section explores in detail how these activities related to the different subgoals of the Youth Goal no.1.

2.1. Summary of Activities Related to the First Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1

The first subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 aims to:

Guarantee meaningful youth involvement and dialogue in all stages of EU decision making by improving existing participatory mechanisms and creating new ones.

There were 117 implementation activities which tackled this subgoal. The EU Member States in which the most attention was dedicated to this subgoal were Poland (13% of all implementation activities that covered this subgoal), Germany (9%), Belgium and Portugal (8% each; see Figure 13). Most of the implementation activities related to this subgoal were policy development and dialogue activities and programmes and activities for young people (see Figure 14). The following examples illustrate specific implementation activities related to this subgoal:

Stakeholder	Polish NWG
Title	Establishment of the Youth Policy Council at the Ministry of National Education
Description	By Ministerial Order on 18 September 2025, the Youth Policy Council was established at the Ministry of National Education. It serves as an advisory and consultative body integrating knowledge and experience of public administration, expert environments, and youth representatives. The Council includes representatives of ministries, public institutions, NGOs, and youth organizations actively working with children and young people. Its creation is a key step toward initiating permanent dialogue between government administration and young citizens, ensuring young people's voices and needs are considered in key public policy areas such as education, climate, security, and technological development.
Aims	To establish a permanent structure for youth participation, enabling youth perspectives to be systematically included in national policymaking and in the development of the National Youth Strategy.

Stakeholder	Belgian (French Community) NWG
Title	Meetings between MEPs and federal ministers with the three BE NYCs and youth delegates (as part of the new 2024–2029 legislative term)
Description	MEPs and federal Ministers have been receptive and were interested in our work and our capacity to collaborate between the three BE NYCs. Some recommendations were taken into account in the work or reflections of decision-makers. They were all keen to organise a meeting with young people from the three Speaking-Communities to discuss the results of Cycle 11 at the end of the cycle (spring 2026). They now identify the NYCs as key players to contact when it comes to youth issues.
Aims	The aim of these meetings is twofold: To present the Youth Councils and their actions at European level (i.e. the mandates of the EUYD and within the YFJ) and to discuss the topics/issues that policy-makers are working on (informing them of our policy recommendations, if any, or identifying areas for collaboration to feed into their work). Finally, the aim was also to propose organising a meeting with young people at the end of the EUYD Cycle to discuss the results of the consultations.

Figure 13: Shares of Implementation Activities Related to the First Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

Note: Cyprus could not be represented due to technical limitations of the software, and its reported activities amounted to 2%. Belgium submitted three reports, one for each community, and the figure shown on the map above is a sum of activities from all three reports.

Figure 14: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity Related to the First Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

2.2. Summary of Activities Related to the Second Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1

The second subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 aims to:

Ensure equal access to quality impartial and youth-friendly information about how the EU works, how to engage in it and what opportunities it offers.

There were 105 implementation activities which tackled this subgoal. The EU Member States in which the most attention was dedicated to this subgoal were Slovakia (9% of all implementation activities that covered this subgoal), Sweden (7%), and the Netherlands (7%; see Figure 15). Most of the implementation activities related to this subgoal were general information or awareness raising campaigns concerning the EU Youth Dialogue as such and the European Youth Goal no.1 in particular, and also programmes and activities for young people (see Figure 16). The following examples illustrate specific implementation activities related to this subgoal:

Stakeholder	Swedish NWG
Title	Podcast: Ung Agenda (Young Agenda)
Description	<p>Two podcast episodes has already been published that presented the outcomes of the consultation phase, and about representation in youth engagement towards EU in Sweden.</p> <p>Several more episodes are being and will be recorded and shared throughout the rest of the year. One with decision maker.</p>
Aims	Dissemination of results to youth organisations and the public.

Stakeholder	Dutch NWG
Title	1. EyoU: Bringing youth to Brussels
Description	<p>During the EyoU activity, a group of young people from the Netherlands travelled to Brussels by train to engage directly with EU and Dutch stakeholders. The programme is designed as a structured learning and dialogue visit that combined (1) youth preparation and reflection, and (2) direct conversations with policymakers and institutional representatives.</p> <p>In Brussels, the group held meetings with the Dutch Permanent Representation to the EU, representatives of the European Commission, and Dutch Members of the European Parliament. These sessions created space for young people to ask informed questions, share experiences from their own realities, and discuss how EU policymaking works in practice, where decisions are made, how priorities are set, and how young people can meaningfully influence those processes. The discussions also explored concrete participation routes, including the EU Youth Dialogue, and what makes youth participation feel accessible, impactful, and respectful of young people's time and expertise.</p> <p>The train journey served as a deliberate part of the methodology: it enabled a collective briefing (agreeing on themes, questions, and key messages), peer exchange and confidence-building, and a structured debrief afterwards. This helped participants translate</p>

	what they learned into clearer follow-up ideas for how EU opportunities and youth participation channels can be communicated to peers in the Netherlands, and how insights from Brussels can be connected to national-level engagement.
Aims	To strengthen meaningful youth–policymaker dialogue and reduce the perceived distance between young people and EU decision-making. The activity aimed to increase young people’s understanding of how EU institutions work, what channels exist for youth participation, and how the EU Youth Dialogue can function as a bridge between young people’s experiences and policy discussions. By facilitating direct, high-quality conversations with key stakeholders in Brussels, the initiative also aimed to build confidence and a sense of agency among participants, and to generate clearer, practical ideas for follow-up communication and engagement with young people in the Netherlands.

Figure 15: Shares of Implementation Activities Related to the Second Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

Note: Cyprus could not be represented due to technical limitations of the software, and its reported activities amounted to 5%. Belgium submitted three reports, one for each community, and the figure shown on the map above is a sum of activities from all three reports.

Figure 16: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity Related to the Second Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

2.3. Summary of Activities Related to the Third Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1

The third subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 aims to:

Introduce and increase education about Europe and the EU in formal and non-formal settings.

There were 91 implementation activities which tackled this subgoal. The EU Member States in which the most attention was dedicated to this subgoal were Slovakia (11% of all implementation activities that covered this subgoal), Sweden and Spain (10% each), and Belgium (7%; see Figure 17). Most of the implementation activities related to this subgoal were general information or awareness raising campaigns concerning the EU Youth Dialogue as such and the European Youth Goal no.1 in particular, and also programmes and activities for young people (see Figure 18). The following examples illustrate specific implementation activities related to this subgoal:

Stakeholder	Belgian (Flemish) NWG
Title	Educational series on TikTok
Description	We will soon launch an educational TikTok series in which our EU Youth Representatives and board members explain the EU Youth Dialogue (EUYD) in an accessible and youth-friendly way. In the videos, they break down what the EUYD is, what has been discussed and agreed in previous cycles and what impact the process has on European and national policies. They also share their own role in the consultations, policy meetings and EU Youth Conferences, and highlight how young people who are consulted contribute to shaping European decisions.
Aims	To make the EUYD more visible, understandable and relatable for a wider group of young people. Our dream is to strengthen awareness, understanding and engagement, so that more young people feel informed, involved and represented in European decision-making.

Stakeholder	Czech NWG
Title	EU and You: Interactive Workshops in Secondary Schools and Training of Young Ambassadors
Description	As part of the EU and You project, five interactive workshops were held at secondary schools across the Czech Republic, led by young ambassadors trained by the Centre for Participation. The programme was created in response to the low level of awareness among young people about how the European Union functions and the opportunities it offers. The EU Youth Dialogue delegates first developed the methodology, trained a group of young facilitators, and jointly created the educational materials and presentations. The training was based on participation competences, facilitation skills, group work, apolitical principles, and safe-space rules, as outlined in the project's methodology. The workshops themselves lasted 60–90 minutes and followed a unified structure: an introductory “opinion barometer”, a short “EU in a nutshell” segment, opportunities for

	<p>young people (e.g. Erasmus+, ESC, DiscoverEU), and work with European values (human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, rule of law, human rights, solidarity, responsibility).</p> <p>The workshops were conducted in a spirit of openness, apolitical communication, and non-formal education “by young people for young people”. Each ambassador had the possibility to adapt the content to the specific school, student group, or regional context.</p> <p>The project also includes ongoing evaluation, mentoring of ambassadors, and continuous development of materials, including a trainer’s handbook and the EU Guide.</p>
Aims	<p>The aim of the programme is to increase students’ awareness of how the EU functions, strengthen their understanding of its values, and present the concrete opportunities it offers to young people. The project supports critical thinking, media literacy, and civic engagement.</p> <p>At the same time, it develops the competences of the young ambassadors – facilitation, group work, communication, project management, and evaluation. The programme therefore provides a dual benefit: it supports active young facilitators while also delivering accessible and understandable information to a wide group of students.</p>

Figure 17: Shares of Implementation Activities Related to the Third Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

Note: Cyprus could not be represented due to technical limitations of the software, and its reported activities amounted to 5%. Belgium submitted three reports, one for each community, and the figure shown on the map above is a sum of activities from all three reports.

Figure 18: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity Related to the Third Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

2.4. Summary of Activities Related to the Fourth Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1

The fourth subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 aims to:

Guarantee fair representation of all member states in political and administrative EU bodies, in line with the principle of equal citizenship.

There were 8 implementation activities which tackled this subgoal. The EU Member States in which the most attention was dedicated to this subgoal were Belgium (25% of all implementation activities that covered this subgoal), and Spain (25%; see Figure 19). Most of the implementation activities related to this subgoal were programmes and activities for young people and also general information or awareness raising campaigns concerning the EU Youth Dialogue as such and the European Youth Goal no.1 in particular (see Figure 20). The following examples illustrate specific implementation activities related to this subgoal:

Stakeholder	Cypriot NWG
Title	Capacity-building activities aimed at developing young people's civic competencies and strengthening their understanding of EU values
Description	<p>The National Working Group (NWG) implements a series of capacity-building activities aimed at strengthening young people's citizenship skills and enhancing their understanding of EU values, democratic processes, and participation opportunities.</p> <p>The activities include interactive workshops and training sessions delivered through participatory and non-formal education methods. Key topics address active citizenship, youth rights, EU decision-making processes, democratic participation, and the role of young people in shaping policies at national and European levels. Particular emphasis is placed on developing critical thinking, civic awareness, and understanding of core EU values such as inclusion, equality, solidarity, and transparency.</p> <p>The capacity-building activities are linked to ongoing initiatives such as the EU Youth Dialogue and youth advocacy actions, enabling participants to apply their knowledge and skills in real consultation and policy-making contexts. This practical approach helps bridge the gap between information, engagement, and action.</p> <p>By equipping young people with knowledge, skills, and confidence, the activity contributes to strengthening trust in the EU project, promoting informed participation, and supporting the development of engaged young citizens who can contribute meaningfully to democratic life within their communities.</p>
Aims	The activity aims to strengthen young people's citizenship skills and deepen their understanding of EU values and democratic processes. Through capacity-building activities, it empowers young people to become informed and active citizens, promotes youth-friendly access to information, and supports meaningful youth participation in decision-making at local, national, and European levels.

Stakeholder	Finnish NWG
Title	Round table about the future of the EU
Description	The EU Youth Delegates organized this event with the Grand Committee that is responsible for EU affairs in the Finnish Parliament. A group of Finnish MPs, MEPs, young people and retired policy makers gathered at the parliament to discuss the next 30 years of the Finnish membership in the European Union while honouring the previous 30. The discussion touched especially on security and global affairs and was facilitated by the EU Youth Delegates. The EUYD was also introduced in the event.
Aims	To promote intergenerational co-operation in EU affairs and to make policy makers more aware of the views and ideas of the young people of today.

Figure 19: Shares of Implementation Activities Related to the Fourth Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

Note: Cyprus could not be represented due to technical limitations of the software, and its reported activities amounted to 13%. Belgium submitted three reports, one for each community, and the figure shown on the map above is a sum of activities from all three reports.

Figure 20: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity Related to the Fourth Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

2.5. Summary of Activities Related to the Fifth Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1

The fifth subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 aims to:

Increase the budget and the impact of the EU youth programmes.

There were 26 implementation activities which tackled this subgoal. The EU Member States in which the most attention was dedicated to this subgoal were Belgium (35% of all implementation activities that covered this subgoal), and Austria (12%; see Figure 21). Most of the implementation activities related to this subgoal were policy developments and advocacy campaigns as well as general information or awareness raising campaigns concerning the EU Youth Dialogue as such (see Figure 22). The following examples illustrate specific implementation activities related to this subgoal:

Stakeholder	Austrian NWG
Title	Austrian EU Youth Dialogue Meets Brussels: Taking the results to the EU level
Description	Since the results of the Youth Dialogue also have relevance at the European level, we aim to engage with decision-makers of the EU-level as well. To achieve this, we are planning a trip in February 2026 with representatives from several of our member organizations, the Board of the Austrian National Youth Council, and the European Youth Delegates. The main objective of the trip is to meet with Austrian MEPs and discuss key topics such as Erasmus+, the EU Youth Strategy, and the regulation and use of social media. Beyond these discussions, the trip will provide participants with the opportunity to gain first-hand insight into the functioning of EU institutions, fostering a better understanding of European decision-making processes. A meeting with YFJ is also planned. Through this experience, we aim to empower young people, enhance their knowledge of EU structures, and promote active engagement in shaping policies that affect youth across Europe.
Aims	In line with Youth Goal #1 – Connecting the EU with Youth – the activity is designed to strengthen the link between young people and EU policies, enabling participants to see how their perspectives and contributions can influence decision-making at the European level.

Stakeholder	Slovenian NWG
Title	Meetings with decision-makers
Description	We are currently organising meetings with decision-makers. So far, we have presented our recommendations to the Council of the Government of the Republic of Slovenia for Youth. We have secured meetings with the Minister of Education and the Minister of Digital Transformation, along with both National Agencies for Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps. Additionally, we plan to engage with associations of local communities to discuss youth participation mechanisms and activities at the local level. We will also reach out to the Club of Young Parliamentarians.
Aims	To secure commitment and support from decision-makers and key stakeholders to ensure the implementation of at least certain aspects of the recommendations.

Figure 21: Shares of Implementation Activities Related to the Fifth Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

Note: Cyprus could not be represented due to technical limitations of the software, and its reported activities amounted to 0%. Belgium submitted three reports, one for each community, and the figure shown on the map above is a sum of activities from all three reports.

Figure 22: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity Related to the Fifth Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

2.6. Summary of Activities Related to the Sixth Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1

The sixth subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 aims to:

Build young people’s trust in the EU project by addressing the democratic deficit, lack of transparency and visibility.

There were 89 implementation activities which tackled this subgoal. The EU Member States in which the most attention was dedicated to this subgoal were Belgium (15% of all implementation activities that covered this subgoal), Poland and Portugal (10% each), and the Czech Republic (9%; see Figure 23). Most of the implementation activities related to this subgoal were programmes and activities for young people, dialogue activities between young people and policymakers, and general information or awareness raising campaigns concerning the EU Youth Dialogue as such (see Figure 24). The following examples illustrate specific implementation activities related to this subgoal:

Stakeholder	Latvian NWG
Title	“Es un ES iespējas” (Me and EU Opportunities)
Description	<p>The activity “Es un ES iespējas” took place on 16 January 2026 at the ARPC “Zeimuļš” youth centre in Rēzekne as a regional EU Youth Dialogue event in the Latgale region. A total of 51 young people participated, representing diverse ages, backgrounds, and social groups, including young people from minority groups, NEET backgrounds, and young people with disabilities. The activity was implemented by European Youth Dialogue ambassadors in cooperation with local youth centres, municipalities, and youth workers.</p> <p>The event was structured into two main parts. In the first part, participants worked in facilitated groups to identify and analyse key challenges related to access to information about the European Union and youth opportunities. Young people discussed barriers such as unsuitable communication channels, overly complex language, lack of youth work capacity, limited school involvement, unequal access in rural areas, fragmented information flows, and low motivation caused by information overload and lack of support.</p> <p>In the second part of the event, each group developed concrete, practical solution proposals addressing one of the identified challenges. These included recommendations for youth-friendly communication formats, centralised information platforms, stronger cooperation between schools and youth organisations, improved support for youth workers, better outreach in rural areas, and early introduction of EU-related information in education. The solutions were presented and discussed collectively, allowing participants to refine ideas and understand how their proposals could contribute to youth policy development.</p> <p>Throughout the activity, EJD ambassadors moderated discussions, ensured inclusive participation, and supported young people in translating their experiences into structured recommendations. The event concluded with reflection, during which participants recognised their role in shaping improvements to youth information systems.</p>
Aims	The primary aim of the activity was to assess and improve young people’s access to clear, timely, and youth-friendly information about the European Union and the opportunities it offers, particularly in the Latgale region. The initiative sought to identify systemic barriers that limit youth participation and to co-create practical solutions together with young people.

	<p>Another key aim was to strengthen meaningful dialogue between young people and youth policy stakeholders by involving decision-makers, youth workers, and partner organisations in discussions based on young people’s real-life experiences. Through this dialogue, the activity aimed to ensure that youth perspectives are reflected in future policy considerations and information strategies.</p> <p>The activity also aimed to empower young people by increasing their confidence, sense of agency, and understanding of their role within the European Union. By engaging them in structured problem-solving and solution development, the initiative encouraged young people to move from identifying challenges to proposing actionable changes.</p> <p>Additionally, the event aimed to reduce inequalities in access to information and participation by addressing the needs of young people from rural areas, minority groups, NEET backgrounds, and those facing structural barriers. Finally, the activity sought to promote continued engagement in the EU Youth Dialogue by demonstrating its relevance as a channel for influencing youth-related policies at local, national, and European levels.</p>
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Stakeholder	Irish NWG
Title	Europe House Youth Event
Description	We will host an event in collaboration with the European Parliament Office in Dublin at their venue Europe House. The event will invite young people to come along and hear about the current cycle of EUYD while also having an opportunity to engage with Govt Ministers and MEPs as we explore the EU Youth Goals and consider the opportunities for Ireland and young people as it prepares to hold the Presidency. Young people on the day will have the ‘Europa Experience’ which is a unique and innovative interactive space which brings them into the European Parliament.
Aims	The aim of this event is to continue the momentum of the EUYD cycle while maximising the huge potential of collaborating with colleagues in Europe House who have a very dynamic space which very much represents Goal 1. Inviting MEPs and the relevant EU Minister also represents a valuable opportunity to show young people that proximity to these elected representatives is available to them through EUYD and in a meaningful way.

Figure 23: Shares of Implementation Activities Related to the Sixth Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no. 1 in the EU Member States.

Note: Cyprus could not be represented due to technical limitations of the software, and its reported activities amounted to 0%. Belgium submitted three reports, one for each community, and the figure shown on the map above is a sum of activities from all three reports.

Figure 24: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity Related to the Sixth Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

2.7. Summary of Activities Related to the Seventh Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1

The seventh subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 aims to:

Institutionalise the assessment of youth-friendliness, impact and effect of EU policies.

There were 45 implementation activities which tackled this subgoal. The EU Member States in which the most attention was dedicated to this subgoal were Portugal (21% of all implementation activities that covered this subgoal), Finland, Sweden and Belgium (9% each; see Figure 25). Most of the implementation activities related to this subgoal were policy development and advocacy activities, and general information or awareness raising campaigns concerning the EU Youth Dialogue as such (see Figure 26). The following examples illustrate specific implementation activities related to this subgoal:

Stakeholder	Swedish NWG
Title	Establishment of an EU Youth Council within LSU
Description	<p>The EU Council shall serve as a platform for LSU's member organisations to build capacity, share experiences and conduct joint horizon scanning, as well as to collaborate on issues related to the EU Youth Dialogue. The Council shall contribute to strengthening the capacity and political influence of the youth movement, in line with LSU's strategy and LSU's EU projects.</p> <p>One of the key objectives is to establish a long-term feedback mechanism in which young people are not only consulted, but also receive feedback from decision-makers:</p> <p>Young people are consulted → views are collected and conveyed to decision-makers → decision-makers provide feedback to young people. Through this process, young people's substantive influence and trust in democratic processes are strengthened.</p> <p>Function and Role of the Council</p> <p>The Council shall:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serve as a coordinating forum for LSU's member organisations on issues related to the EU Youth Dialogue and EU policy. • Act as a capacity-building arena in which member organisations gain knowledge, tools, and opportunities for experience exchange regarding EU decision-making processes and advocacy. • Contribute to LSU's role as a platform for cooperation, visibility, and joint advocacy at the EU level. • Function as a political voice that jointly formulates positions, reports, and demands addressed to EU institutions and Swedish decision-makers.
Aims	To strengthen the capacity and political influence of LSU's member organisations by coordinating engagement with the EU Youth Dialogue, enabling joint learning and advocacy, and ensuring structured feedback between young people and decision-makers.

Stakeholder	Dutch NWG
Title	Motion on Youth Digital Rights and dialogue with European Commission President's Youth Advisory Board
Description	<p>The Dutch Youth Representatives (European Affairs) worked together with the Flemish Youth Council (Vlaamse Jeugdraad) to draft and submit a motion on youth safety and rights in the digital world. The motion titled “Guaranteeing youth safety and rights in the digital world: a call for a balanced approach” was adopted by the European Youth Forum’s General Assembly/Council of Members in Kandersteg (7 and 8 November 2025).</p> <p>The motion argues for an evidence-based approach that protects young people online while safeguarding rights such as privacy, access to information, participation and connection. It warns against blanket, one-size-fits-all restrictions (including measures that can be easily circumvented) and calls for youth agency in digital policymaking. It also highlights the need to address harmful platform elements such as manipulative or excessive design through stronger accountability and more youth-friendly protections (e.g., safer defaults, meaningful user control, and investment in media/platform literacy for young people and adults).</p> <p>Building on this, one of our Youth Representative for European Affairs brought these priorities into EU-level dialogue during the first meeting of the President’s Youth Advisory Board, chaired by Ursula von der Leyen (3 December 2025, Brussels; topic: “Social media and young people”). During this exchange, the motion and its key messages were shared and used as a basis for discussion.</p>
Aims	To influence EU-level discussions on young people’s digital wellbeing and rights by ensuring youth perspectives shape proposals on social media and online safety. The activity aimed to (1) secure broad youth-sector backing for a balanced, evidence-based policy approach, (2) translate youth concerns into concrete calls for action (platform accountability, safer-by-design features, and stronger media literacy), and (3) create direct high-level dialogue with EU decision-makers so youth priorities are visible, taken seriously, and followed up through ongoing policy processes.

Figure 25: Shares of Implementation Activities Related to the Seventh Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

Note: Cyprus could not be represented due to technical limitations of the software, and its reported activities amounted to 0%. Belgium submitted three reports, one for each community, and the figure shown on the map above is a sum of activities from all three reports.

Figure 26: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity Related to the Seventh Subgoal of the European Youth Goal no.1 in the EU Member States.

3. What Activities Were Implemented in the EU candidate countries?

This section summarises implementation activities collected and submitted by representatives of the EU candidate countries, namely Moldova and Montenegro. In total, these two countries submitted 3 implementation activities.

Figure 27 shows that two out of three implementation activities were reported by the Moldovan representatives, while one out of three was reported by the Montenegrin ones. Most of the reported implementation activities were deliberations between young people and policymakers, and creation of participatory structures (see Figure 28). Two out of three implementation activities dealt with the following subgoals of the European Youth Goal no.1:

- Guarantee meaningful youth involvement and dialogue in all stages of EU decision making by improving existing participatory mechanisms and creating new ones.
- Ensure equal access to quality impartial and youth-friendly information about how the EU works, how to engage in it and what opportunities it offers.
- Introduce and increase education about Europe and the EU in formal and non-formal settings.
- Build young people’s trust in the EU project by addressing the democratic deficit, lack of transparency and visibility.

Only one of the recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland) was covered by the implementation activities in the EU candidate countries, namely:

- Strengthening youth engagement in decision-making through measures such as youth led European Citizenship initiatives, Youth check at national and European level and the EU Youth Dialogue.

Two of the recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark) were covered by implementation activities of the EU candidate countries, namely:

- Ensuring a dedicated space for youth volunteering and solidarity.
- Addressing external challenges facing young people.

The following examples illustrate specific implementation activities reported by the EU candidate countries:

Stakeholder	Moldovan representatives
Title	Strengthening Structured Youth Participation in Public Decision-Making
Description	<p>During the period 2025–2026, the National Youth Council of Moldova (CNTM) carried out a comprehensive process of reviewing and reforming the functioning mechanism of the Youth Advisory Group attached to the United Nations in the Republic of Moldova. In 2025, the working methodology of this mechanism was completely redesigned, emphasizing the clarification of the mandate, transparent selection criteria, well-defined responsibilities and a functional relationship with UN agencies. As a direct result of this process, in 2026 a new Advisory Group was created consisting of 5 young people, selected on the basis of competence, representativeness and motivation, which actively contributes to the integration of the youth perspective in UN initiatives and processes at the national level.</p> <p>In parallel, the CNTM initiated the development of an innovative mechanism for structured dialogue between young people and public institutions, by creating the Youth Advisory Commission attached to the ministries, with the aim of ensuring the "youth-friendly" nature</p>

	<p>of public policies and normative acts. This commission has the role of analyzing and formulating recommendations on policy documents from the perspective of their impact on young people, contributing to reducing inequities and aligning state measures with the real needs of young people. The mechanism is to be piloted by the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection, under the coordination of the CNTM, with the intention of creating a replicable and sustainable model for other public institutions.</p> <p>CNTM, with the support of the Danish Youth Council (DUF) and in partnership with the Moldovan Office for European Integration, formed the Youth Advisory Group for European Integration. A first activity of the group was a visit to Denmark. The participants had meetings with public institutions, youth organizations and Danish political actors, exploring models of youth involvement in decision-making processes, European policies and international cooperation.</p>
Aims	<p>The aim of the initiative was to strengthen structured and meaningful youth participation in institutional decision-making processes by reforming and formalising youth advisory mechanisms at national level. The action sought to ensure that young people's perspectives are systematically integrated into the work of international organisations and public institutions, through transparent, representative, and functional advisory structures.</p>

Stakeholder	Montenegrin representatives
Title	EU Youth Dialogue
Description	<p>During the action, the EU Youth Dialogue on the Green Agenda is promoted and implemented through a combination of outreach, youth consultations, and structured dialogue activities. The initiative begins with a youth-friendly communication campaign explaining what the EU Youth Dialogue is, why young people are being consulted, and how their input will be used. Promotion is carried out through social media channels, youth networks, schools, universities, youth clubs, and local partners, with a focus on reaching young people from different regions and backgrounds.</p> <p>The action then continues with consultation activities such as focus groups, local outreach dialogues, and an online questionnaire. These formats allow young people to share their experiences, challenges, and recommendations related to key Green Agenda topics (climate action, circular economy, biodiversity, sustainable mobility, and pollution reduction). The collected inputs are documented and summarised into youth-driven recommendations.</p> <p>The process concludes with a national final event that presents the main findings and enables structured dialogue between young people and institutions. The ministry and relevant stakeholders are engaged in the follow-up, ensuring that youth recommendations are connected to ongoing policy processes.</p> <p>The Green Agenda is especially relevant in Montenegro as an EU candidate country, since progress in Chapter 27 (Environment and Climate Change) is a key requirement for advancing EU accession and is strongly linked to closing other negotiation chapters. Through this action, young people are empowered to contribute to Montenegro's green transition and EU integration by providing concrete policy recommendations and strengthening dialogue with decision-makers.</p>
Aims	<p>The aim of the action is to establish the EU Youth Dialogue as a sustainable and recognized participation mechanism in Montenegro, using the Green Agenda as a relevant and timely policy framework. Through this initiative, young people are meaningfully</p>

involved in discussions on environmental and climate-related policies that directly affect their lives and Montenegro's EU accession process.

The action seeks to strengthen structured dialogue between young people and institutions, ensuring that youth perspectives on Green Agenda priorities are systematically collected, validated, and linked to policy development. By focusing on the Green Agenda, the initiative connects youth participation with one of the most important reform areas for Montenegro as an EU candidate country, particularly in the context of Chapter 27 (Environment and Climate Change).

At the same time, the action aims to build institutional practices, capacities, and trust needed for the long-term implementation of the EU Youth Dialogue in Montenegro, beyond a single cycle or topic.

Figure 27: Shares of Implementation Activities in the EU candidate countries.

Figure 28: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity in the EU candidate countries.

4. What Activities Were Implemented by IYNGOs?

This section summarises impacts collected and submitted by representatives of international youth NGOs (IYNGOs), namely AEGEE-Europe and Erasmus Student Network (ESN). In total, these two IYNGOs submitted 7 implementation activities.

Figure 29 shows that about three quarters of implementation activities were reported by AEGEE-Europe representatives, while about one quarter was reported by the Erasmus Student Network. All of the reported implementation activities were programmes and activities for young people, and some of them also provided opportunities for dialogue, information dissemination, and capacity building (see Figure 30).

The four following subgoals of the European Youth Goal no.1 were covered by the implementation activities reported by the IYNGOs (see Figure 31):

- Introduce and increase education about Europe and the EU in formal and non-formal settings.
- Ensure equal access to quality impartial and youth-friendly information about how the EU works, how to engage in it and what opportunities it offers.
- Build young people’s trust in the EU project by addressing the democratic deficit, lack of transparency and visibility.
- Guarantee meaningful youth involvement and dialogue in all stages of EU decision making by improving existing participatory mechanisms and creating new ones.

Only one of the recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland) was covered by the implementation activities by the IYNGOs, namely:

- Strengthening youth engagement in decision-making through measures such as youth led European Citizenship initiatives, Youth check at national and European level and the EU Youth Dialogue.

Two of the recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark) were covered by implementation activities by the IYNGOs, namely:

- Ensuring a dedicated space for youth volunteering and solidarity.
- Addressing external challenges facing young people.

The following examples illustrate specific implementation activities reported by the IYNGOs:

Stakeholder	AEGEE-Europe (IYNGO)
Title	Model European Union 2026 [Planned]
Description	Simulation of European Union politics and its legislative procedures. Participants are divided into various branches of the political ecosystem on the European level and will simulate their work over the course of these few days. The event will inform European youth in an engaging and comprehensive manner about relevant issues that Europe is facing and explain how the European Union and other institutions work.
Aims	To inform European youth in an engaging and comprehensive manner about relevant issues that Europe is facing and explain how the European Union and other institutions work.

Stakeholder	Erasmus Student Network (IYNGO)
Title	Erasmus Generation Meeting 2026 Split
Description	<p>The Erasmus Generation Meeting 2026 is a planned large-scale European youth event bringing together young people, student representatives, youth leaders, practitioners, and institutional stakeholders active in the fields of education, mobility, volunteering and youth participation.</p> <p>The event is designed around a clear thematic framework, Shaping Skills through Student Mobility, and structured through participatory and dialogue-oriented methodologies such as Knowledge Hubs, Campfire Sessions, Ignite Sessions and Collaboration Incubators. These formats are specifically chosen to foster active participation, peer learning, collective reflection and the co-creation of ideas and proposals.</p> <p>Through these sessions, participants will engage in discussions on the future of international mobility, skills development, recognition of learning outcomes, youth engagement and cooperation with institutions. The event aims to provide young people with the space, tools and confidence to express their perspectives on European-level priorities, to better understand EU policy frameworks affecting them, and to strengthen their ability to engage in structured dialogue and advocacy processes beyond the event itself.</p>
Aims	<p>The Erasmus Generation Meeting 2026 aims to contribute to the implementation of the EU Youth Dialogue by embedding its principles directly into the design and methodology of the event.</p> <p>The planned aims are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • empower young people to actively participate in dialogue on European policies related to education, mobility, volunteering and skills development; • strengthen young people’s competences for civic engagement, critical thinking and participation in democratic processes at European level; • support youth organisations and stakeholders in developing inclusive, participatory and youth-centred approaches to dialogue and policy engagement; • foster mutual understanding and trust between young people and institutional actors by creating structured, safe and participatory spaces for exchange.

Figure 29: Shares of Implementation Activities by the IYNGOs.

Figure 30: Shares of Activity Types per Implementation Activity by the IYNGOs.

Figure 31: Shares of European Youth Goal no.1 Subgoals Covered in Implementation Activities by the IYNGOs.

5. What Activities Were Implemented by the EU Stakeholders?

Four EU-level actors also reported on activities they implemented. Reports were submitted by representatives of two of the countries that are currently part of the Trio of the Presidency of the Council of the EU, namely Denmark and Poland; by representatives of the European Commission, specifically the Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture (DG EAC); and by the representatives of the European Youth Forum (YFJ).

The Danish Presidency of the Council of the EU contributed to the EUYD11 implementation phase via the following activities:

- Presentation at the Youth Working Party meeting
 - At the Youth Working Party meeting on the 11th of July a presentation was held by a representative of the Ukrainian National Youth Council and of the Danish Youth Council on the different cooperation projects between the two organisations, showcasing concrete examples of transnational youth cooperation and youth-led solidarity initiatives.
- The EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen
 - The EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen was at the core of the implementation of the EU Youth Dialogue in the 11th cycle, with a strong focus on political impact and follow-up. Building on the EU Youth Goal No. 1 (“Connecting the EU with Youth”), the conference translated young people’s inputs into concrete policy recommendations for the future Erasmus+ programme (2028–2034).
- Youth Council meeting and Youth Breakfast
 - The Youth Breakfast ahead of the EYCS Council meeting between youth representatives, European decision-makers and stakeholders served as a follow-up and political mainstreaming activity for the EU Youth Dialogue. The theme was “Promoting resilience and engagement among young Europeans”.

The Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU contributed to the EUYD11 implementation phase via the following activities:

- Youth recommendations from the EU Youth Conference in Lublin reflected in a Council of the EU policy outcome
 - Youth recommendations developed at the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (March 2025) were reflected in the Council of the European Union Conclusions entitled “*Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on a community of young people in Europe based on European values for a common and safe Europe*”, adopted by the Council of the EU (Education, Youth, Culture and Sport) on 12 May 2025.
- Adoption by the Council of the EU of the Resolution on EU Youth Dialogue governance
 - On 12–13 May 2025, the Council of the European Union (Education, Youth, Culture and Sport) adopted a Resolution updating the governance of the EU Youth Dialogue. This Resolution strengthens the implementation of the EU Youth Dialogue by enhancing the role of young people and National Working Groups in dialogue with decision-makers, ensuring that consultation outcomes are effectively translated into policy.
- The introduction of civic education as a compulsory subject within formal education in Poland
 - Since September 2025 civic education has been introduced as a compulsory subject in Polish schools in line with youth recommendations formulated during the EU Youth Conference in Lublin. This concrete national-level measure supports the development of young people’s civic competences in line with European Youth Goal #1.
- The Minister of Education announced the development of the National Youth Strategy and established the Youth Policy Council
 - The engagement of the Minister of Education in EU Youth Dialogue activities conducted during Poland’s Presidency of the Council of the EU, including the EU Youth Conference

in Lublin and the Informal Youth Breakfast, contributed to the advancement of youth policy in Poland.

The European Commission, specifically the Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture (DG EAC) contributed to the EUYD11 implementation phase via the following activities:

- Follow-up on the EUYD11 recommendations
 - All recommendations from the EU Youth Dialogue are first assessed to check which ones are relevant at the EU level by DG EAC. All EU-level recommendations are then shared with relevant departments (depending on topic), across the EU institutions and to stakeholders. EUYD outcomes were also included in the preparation of Commission initiatives going through the youth check and referenced in policy documents. Examples include the Commission's Communication on the European Democracy Shield, the Strategy for Civil Society and the Equality Union: strategy for LGBTQI equality.
 - Special attention was given to the recommendations regarding the EU Youth Dialogue from the conference in Lublin as they were timely and aligned with the *Council Resolution on the revised governance of the EU Youth Dialogue* and with the efforts of the DG EAC to strengthen the EU Youth Dialogue as a follow-up on the European Year of Youth. Several recommendations have led to concrete outcomes, including a physical meeting for NWG (planned for May 2026), advice on diversity and inclusion as well as upcoming new guidelines for monitoring and follow-up. Input from DG EAC's consultation session was also fed into the Strategy on Intergenerational Fairness (published in March 2026).
- Support of the Policy Development Efforts
 - DG EAC facilitated contacts between the European Parliament and the Danish National Youth Council. Representatives from the Danish National Youth Council met with DG EAC Director-General Pia Ahrenkilde Hansen to present the outcomes.
 - For the first time, DG EAC will host a whole working group at the EU Youth Conference in Nicosia (Cyprus). It will focus on the revision of the EU Youth Strategy, strengthening voices of young people in setting up the future EU-wide youth policy.

The European Youth Forum (YFJ) contributed to the EUYD11 implementation phase via the following activities:

- Dissemination of the conference outcomes (policy paper):
 - Member organisations of the European Youth Forum
 - Youth organisations and youth stakeholders via the European Youth Forum's newsletter
 - CULT Secretariat in the European Parliament
- Meetings with stakeholders:
 - Minister Marina Ferrari (France) – Discussions on Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps, including mention of the Danish Policy Paper on the EUYC outcomes.
 - Minister Andrea Abodi (Italy) – Discussions on Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps, including mention of the Danish Policy Paper on the EUYC outcomes.
 - Youth ministries/permanent representations working on the new version of Erasmus+ post-2027
 - Germany
 - Sweden
 - Netherlands
 - Malta
 - Cyprus
 - National agencies network
 - S&D cult event on empowering young people across Europe
- Communication on social media
 - Several stories and posts regarding the EU Youth Conferences, Erasmus+ demands

6. How Could the Implementation Phase of the EUYD be Further Improved?

23 stakeholders also responded to the following question:

HOW COULD THE IMPLEMENTATION PHASE OF THE EUYD BE FURTHER IMPROVED, BASED ON THE EXPERIENCES OF AND CHALLENGES FACED BY YOUR NWG?

21 of the stakeholders were NWGs based in EU Member States, one represented a EU candidate country, and one was an IYNGO. This chapter summarises the key points raised by EU Member States and IYNGOs relating to future improvements of the implementation phase of the EUYD, while the views of the EU candidate countries are separately summarised in the last paragraph.

Importance of further improving practical matters such as timelines and funding was mentioned by some stakeholders. It was suggested to simplify reporting, and to make timely decisions on the overall EUYD cycle timeline, including deadlines. Some stakeholders suggested disseminating information on the upcoming timeline and aims of the EUYD cycle before it starts, and to continuously share updated information by the European Steering Group to keep all stakeholders in the loop on the upcoming activities and their link to the overall EUYD cycle (e.g., how the EU Youth Conference topics relate to the overall topics of the cycle, etc.). Some stakeholders went as far as to suggest prolonging the implementation phase or the EUYD cycle itself to allow for implementation activities to be properly planned, implemented, and reported on. This also relates to the issue of reporting long-term implementation activities which span more than one cycle of the EUYD, and also with the issue of dealing with EUYD recommendations before they are cemented in Council Conclusions or Resolutions. It is equally key to receive funds in a timely manner. Late payments of the EUYD grants and uncertainties related to national co-funding create unnecessary risks and require stakeholders to pre-finance the EUYD activities and hope it will get covered eventually.

“Although the project officially started in January 2025 (with the opening of the 11th cycle under the Polish Presidency), the grant was only transferred in August. As a result, key activities — including the consultation campaign reaching 1,529 young people and the recruitment for the Ambassadors and Consulates/Embassies Networks — had to be pre-financed from PROM’s own resources and those of its partners. This situation generated significant financial risk and uncertainty from the very beginning of the implementation phase.

In parallel, since the start of the project, we have been in ongoing discussions with the Ministry of National Education regarding the required 20% national co-funding. The continued lack of a formal decision further delays planning and undermines the secure financial management of the project. PROM may be forced to launch a public fundraising campaign to cover the 20% co-funding, as was the case in previous project cycles.” (Polish NWG)

Earmarking certain part of the overall EUYD funding to the implementation phase and allowing for funding of long-term initiatives would also help support the implementation activities designed by various actors. It was also suggested to support short-term policy piloting projects, so that the EUYD can act not only as idea generator, but also as a policy incubator and as a valuable partner in evidence-based policymaking.

“In addition, allowing EUYD funding to support longer-term pilot actions or policy testing linked to recommendations could significantly enhance impact. Small-scale pilot projects can provide practical evidence on the feasibility and effectiveness of NWG-led proposals before wider policy adoption. Supporting such pilots would also help bridge the gap between strategic recommendations and real-world implementation, while offering decision-makers concrete examples of how EUYD outcomes can inform policy development. Over time, this approach could strengthen the credibility of the EUYD as a tool for evidence-based youth policymaking.” (Maltese NWG)

Contingency planning for situations when funding is not readily available may be one of the options to explore in order to support the stakeholders in effectively engaging in EUYD despite potential financial uncertainty. This may be achieved, for example, by setting up long-term EUYD structures at the national levels.

“Strengthening the institutional embedding of the EUYD within national youth governance frameworks would also enhance implementation. Clearly defined roles, stable coordination structures and permanent contact points among ministries, national youth councils and youth agencies can foster continuity, shared ownership and sustained engagement beyond individual cycles. In this regard, following the example of the European Youth Forum’s role as the EUYD Secretariat, as planned for the start of the 12th cycle, the establishment and maintenance of dedicated secretariat functions, combined with structured onboarding procedures for future presidencies, would be crucial to strengthening institutional memory, ensuring continuity and supporting long-term knowledge transfer among EUYD stakeholders.” (Greek NWG)

Support of international cooperation was seen as a key desired change by several stakeholders.

Some argued that strengthening cooperation between the NWGs and the IYNGOs might present valuable opportunities, as it would allow the NWGs to build on the expertise of the IYNGOs in certain areas. Others argued that it may be impossible to implement EUYD recommendations which relate to the EU level by single NWGs. Therefore, options for cooperation of NWGs on transnational activities should be explored. Lastly, aligning EUYD activities with other key youth events in the EU and on the national levels was also suggested as a powerful tool to creating impact.

“Greater support for creating space and opportunities for cross-country implementation activities could help address this, encouraging collaboration, sharing of best practices, and alignment between NWGs. Strengthening coordination in this way would make the implementation phase more coherent, impactful, and closely connected to the overall goals of the EU Youth Dialogue.” (Danish NWG)

Capacity building was seen as key by many stakeholders. External capacity building and support, as well as ways of supporting peer learning amongst the NWGs and continuous communication and idea sharing were mentioned. Some stakeholders would also appreciate more support from the colleagues at the European Commission, namely in the domain of communication and visibility (e.g., using the official EUYD templates across various software solutions, social media support, ready to share dissemination materials, etc.), but also in forms of toolkits, templates, and good practice sharing. A common EUYD library bringing together all past EUYD documents for NWGs to use would be a welcome development as well. Moreover, engaging colleagues from other sectors was mentioned as an important, yet potentially challenging endeavour. This is, nevertheless, key as many EUYD recommendations span different sectors, and their implementation therefore necessarily needs to be a cross-sectoral initiative.

“Learning from other countries’ experiences would also be highly valuable. Understanding which approaches worked well during the same cycle, as well as the challenges encountered, would help youth networks adopt best practices and avoid common pitfalls. This exchange could become an ongoing practice, for example through a Microsoft Teams chat or another shared platform, ensuring that EUYD does not happen in a vacuum and that participants can stay connected and inspired by each other’s initiatives. Another simple alternative would be to have a table with all social media links, allowing us to follow and check in on our colleagues abroad.” (Latvian NWG)

“Finally, conference outcomes are sometimes broad and cross-cutting. While this reflects the complexity of youth policy, it also means that follow-up may require engagement across multiple ministries and policy domains. For NWGs with limited time and capacity, it is not always feasible to build and maintain entry points across all relevant ministries to ensure that outcomes reach the appropriate policy owners.” (Dutch NWG)

Creating an effective communication system focusing on sharing impacts of the EUYD with the young people was stressed as a key desire by many stakeholders. Communication should also focus on explaining young people (including those with fewer opportunities) how the youth voices influenced the policy reality, and in what ways the ideas generated by young people were used and where their use was limited and why. This topic relates to the fact that there are many actors related to the EUYD implementation, and also to the fact that the EUYD cycles are too short for some implementation activities to take place, and for the policy cycle to happen.

“It is essential that European institutions be more transparent (particularly with youth delegates) with regard to the follow-up given to Council Resolutions or Conclusions drafted under the Presidencies, i.e. the political impact of the recommendations. It’s also important to take into account the long timeframe of the political advocacy work done by the NYC, which often extends beyond the few months dedicated to the implementation phase, and therefore into the next EUYD Cycle. The feeling that the work carried out throughout a cycle has no impact and is not taken into account seriously undermines the legitimacy and meaning of the EUYD at present.” (Belgian French-speaking Community NWG)

More precise definitions and explanations on the desired aims and objectives of the implementation phase of the EUYD would help reduce uncertainty. Some stakeholders suggested that the EUYD implementation phase is not well defined at the moment, and it would benefit from further development and framing. This is also related to “translating” numerous recommendations to activities, and to being coherent within the EUYD cycle across the NWGs and other actors. Better framing of the implementation phase as well as regular check-ins to ensure quality implementation activities were suggested. Recognition of individual learning outcomes was also stressed as an important aspect of the EUYD implementation phase.

“Currently, the phase can feel somewhat abstract, as the framework for action is very broad. While this flexibility allows delegates and NWGs to work creatively and autonomously, it can also create uncertainty about priorities, expectations, and which implementation activities would be most effective on a broader EU scale.” (Danish NWG)

“One thing we consistently struggle with is that ministries don’t always know what exactly they’re expected to follow up after the EUYCs. A simple, standard briefing right after each EUYC, plus a quick mid cycle check in, would already fix a lot of confusion.” (Belgian Flemish NWG)

Lastly, representatives of the EU candidate country (Montenegro) emphasised the fact that processes need to be still put in place, as they implemented the EUYD for the first time. This brings forward challenges in the domains of planning, institutional commitments, and outreach.

Annexes

Recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Lublin (Poland)

- Declaring a European year of resilience and increasing long-term, easily accessible EU funding for youth resilience projects and crisis preparedness.
- Strengthening youth engagement in decision-making through measures such as youth led European Citizenship initiatives, Youth check at national and European level and the EU Youth Dialogue. These should incorporate transparent follow-up processes which track the implementation of policy proposals, as well as partnerships with youth organisations on communication and outreach to reach a diverse range of young people and better enable young leaders to bridge the gap between young people and EU policymakers.
- Encouraging young candidates in elections through measures like quotas, political traineeships lowering the age of eligibility, and giving young people a real chance of getting elected.
- Introducing civic education as a mandatory subject in formal education, with a comprehensive curriculum, delivered and created in co-operation with non-governmental organisations. This should nurture civic responsibility, promote European values, civil society, critical thinking, democratic participation, and the role of democratic institutions.
- Co-designing digital learning frameworks together with young people (formal, non-formal, informal) in domains such as understanding algorithms, media literacy, cybersecurity, fact-checking, digital footprints, information management, critical thinking, ethical media and AI use.
- Implementing transparent verification and accountability processes for social media, as well as media quality labelling to encourage responsible digital behaviour.
- Supporting youth-led businesses and start-ups in the field of social media and AI.

Recommendations coming from the EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen (Denmark)

- Safeguarding a youth chapter with an earmarked budget of 15%
- Distributing Erasmus+ 2028-2034 grants before the start of the mobility
- Ensuring a dedicated space for youth volunteering and solidarity
- Addressing external challenges facing young people
- Creating dedicated Erasmus+ 2028-2034 funding stream for soft skills and citizenship skills
- Simplifying the application and reporting process for Erasmus+ 2028-2034 opportunities
- Promoting preparedness, resilience and peacebuilding through Erasmus+ 2028-2034
- Introducing Erasmus+ Youth as a distinct section within the Erasmus+ 2028-2034